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The spectral analyses of trombone multiphonics, with an outline of the use of these analyses in recent compositions.

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1. The Spectral Analyses of Trombone Multiphonics

- **Introduction**

The research into multiphonics presented here was motivated initially by the consideration of incorporating specific trombone multiphonics into a composition where these phenomena are an integral part of the composition.¹ Multiphonic sounds exist at the border of harmony and timbre, if indeed these two categories are any longer valid as separate domains. Instrumental multiphonics can provide an effective morphological bridge between acoustic and electroacoustic musics and, with the kind of turbulence encountered in a trombone ‘lip’ multiphonic, provide the same sort of complex system behaviour in sound as that studied in Chaos theory in other complex systems. The rich network of harmonic relationships between different multiphonics produced on the same instrument or relationships between multiphonics produced on different instruments can provide the composer with the possibility of finding some gold at the end of the rainbow - that is, a coherent network of relationships with origins in sound itself, rather than theory alone.

The capability of producing multiphonics has become a standard part of the ‘extended’ technique developed by many performers of contemporary music and jazz. However, despite (or even, because of) studies such as Bartolozzi’s “*New Sounds for Woodwind*”² multiphonics are sometimes viewed with suspicion as being unstable, unpredictable and too uniquely dependent on a particular performer/instrument/acoustic space. The result of this caution by composers that the same multiphonic will not be reproducible by any performer

can lead to multiphonic phenomena being used compositionally almost exclusively as an 'effect'³.

While there are certainly significant variations possible between performers, it has been found that in the case of trombone multiphonics there is sufficient justification to assume a reasonable level of consistency between performers.

- **Trombone multiphonics**

There are several distinct types of trombone multiphonic which can be grouped into 2 broad categories⁴:

1. **'Vocal' multiphonics**; where the performer sings/talks/whispers through the instrument while simultaneously playing the instrument. (Examples abound such as Berio's *Sequenza V* and Globokar's *Discours 2* for five trombones).

2. **'Lip' multiphonics**, which are purely instrumental. This group contains three classes:

- 2.1 Multiphonics formed by relaxing the lip while still playing a conventional pitch.

The resulting sound will appear to contain an additional pitch an octave, or a twelfth below the played pitch ($F/2$, $F/3$ where F = played frequency). This type of lip multiphonic most closely resembles the type of vocal production (spoken or sung) termed vocal bitonality, a characteristic of dysphonia (Castellengo et al., 1984)

- 2.2 Multiphonics formed by a change of lip position producing both the pitch being played and simultaneously a neighbouring partial in the same slide position. The formation of this multiphonic has some similarity with 2.3 below but sounds different in being much more harmonic and less complex.

- 2.3 A study of this type of multiphonic by Castellengo, Caussé and Sluchin⁵ (1983) is the starting point to this present research. The essence of the production of this

type of ‘lip’ multiphonic is that it is formed ‘between’ two adjacent partials of a fundamental in a given slide position. In moving into the multiphonic the trombonist ‘decentres’ or ‘bends’ (lowers, or raises) the frequency of the lip, aiming ‘between’ two partials and maintaining normal air pressure. Castellengo et al.⁶ describe three differing perceptions of the sounding multiphonic, varying according to the tessitura and the listener: (a) “...*perception d’un intervalle caractéristique (quarte, tierce, seconde)*; (b) *apparition d’un son très grave situé une ou deux octaves plus basses que le partiel émis*, (c) *sensation mal définie d’un son complexe interrompu régulièrement.*”

- [- perception of a characteristic interval (fourth, third, second),
- the appearance of a very low sound one or two octaves lower than the partial sounded,
- an ill-defined sensation of a complex sound regularly interrupted.]

1.1 Analysis: Trombone Multiphonic 1

Adopting the method given by Castellengo et al. for describing the formulation of the multiphonic: let F and F' be the frequencies of the two adjacent partials where $F > F'$.

In multiphonic 1 $F = 233 \text{ Hz (A\#)}$, $F' = 185 \text{ Hz (F\#)}$.

Sounding $A\#$ (233 Hz) as the 5th partial in slide position V (fundamental $F\#$ 46.6 Hz), and ‘bending’ the frequency down towards the 4th partial $F\#$ produces the multiphonic with the following characteristics:

(i) The ratio of the frequencies can be given in the form: $m / (m - 1)$ (m integer)

corresponding to the ratio F/F' .

Thus $F/F' (A\#/F\#) = 233.082 / 184.997 = 5/4 = 1.25$ (i.e. a major third)

(ii) The new fundamental $F^0 = F / (m + 1) = 233.082 / 6 = 38.8 \text{ Hz (Eb)}$

(iii) The characteristic interval $I = (m + 1) / m = 6 / 5$ i.e. a minor third

The expected multiphonic would be notated:

example 1

played: *multiphonic sounds:*

fundamental

new fundamental (F_0)

Three FFT spectral analyses of three different performances of this multiphonic were made:

- (a) FFT of a 48ms sample taken after the multiphonic has established itself⁷; transform size 2048 with a resolution of 3.9Hz.

The analysis reveals the multiphonic to be a family of harmonics at around 38.27 Hz spacing, with the first 4 components absent (see **Table 1** and **Graph 1a, 1b**)

The characteristic interval **I** (minor 3rd between partials 5 and 6) can be heard with the strongest amplitudes. In **graph,1b** the strongest partial is given a value of 1 and other amplitude strengths are shown relative to this. (For calibration reference, a 1000 Hz sine wave recorded at 90dB would show as 41.9 dB in Table 1, a value of 1.6634 on the graph of relative amplitudes⁸). The analysis provides a useful confirmation of the ‘expected’ multiphonic suggested by the article by Castellengo et al., though the intonation of the partials is not quite so clear-cut; microtonal components arise even with partials 5 and 6 where we find a $\frac{1}{4}$ -flat G (rather than G natural) and a Bb an eight-tone flatter than Bb.

The ‘new’ fundamental 38.27Hz does not appear in the analysis as a frequency in its own right, though it can be heard in the sound. There appears to be a psycho-acoustic phenomenon where the brain perceives this fundamental below the complex of partials in the multiphonic.

The ‘missing’ components 2,3 and 4 are explained by considering the acoustics of the interaction between the harmonic series of the trombone tube itself and the instrumentalist’s lip frequency:

example 2

The image shows musical notation for a trombone. The top staff is in treble clef with a key signature of two flats (Bb, Eb) and a common time signature. It contains several chords, with the word "etc." written above the first and last ones. The bottom staff is in bass clef with the same key signature and time signature. It shows a sequence of notes: a whole note chord (labeled "5 4"), followed by a half note (labeled "5"), and then a quarter note (labeled "4"). A dashed line with an arrow points from the "5" note to the "4" note, with the text "'bending' down towards partial 4" written above it. Below the "4" note, a bracket labeled "I" spans the distance to the next chord. The final chord is labeled "I". Below the notation, three labels are provided: "slide position V of trombone tube." under the first chord, "frequency of lip with harmonics" under the "5" note, and "harmonic series of 'new' fundamental" under the final chord.

Since the trombone is still in the position V the lowest components of the new fundamental will find no resonance from the instrument itself but the higher partials will generate resonance within the tube. Clearly the frequency spacing of the characteristic interval **I** is the critical factor determining the frequency of the 'new' fundamental. In multiphonic 1 the frequency is 38.27Hz.

- **(b)** Spectrographic analysis using the software *Hypersignal* ; FFT of order 2^{12} (transform size: 4096) with a 50% overlap to 2048 using a Hamming window⁹. This analysis allows a view of the complete multiphonic, including the initial Bb 'normal' tone at the beginning and the return to the normal tone at the end. As indicated in the top right corner of the picture (see **spectrograph sm733m**), the *time spanned* is 25.22 seconds; frequency is represented on the vertical axis with each division corresponding to octaves of C natural starting with 130.8Hz as the first division, 261.625Hz ('middle' C) as the second, and so on. The horizontal is divided in this instance into 2.522" steps. The strength of the partials is colour coded in steps of 5dB from white (strongest amplitude), yellow, orange, pink etc..

The performance of the multiphonic analysed here was at a quiet dynamic *p - mp*.

Analysis 1, some 1" into the sound, shows the prominence of partials 2 and 3 of the **Bb**. It can be seen quite clearly on the spectrograph the trombonist 'bending' downward this opening **Bb**: approx. 1.5" into the sound the higher partials fall by *c.* 10Hz. At 3.5" the formation of sideband frequencies commences either side of the **Bb**'s harmonics; analysis 2, 6" into the sound, shows the spectrum just before the multiphonic fully establishes itself (see **graph 2a** and **2b**).

Graph 2b shows the formation of sideband frequencies in relation to the spectrum formed on the 'new' fundamental Eb as predicted in the study by Castellengo et al. previously mentioned. However, as can be seen in **Table 2**, the spectrum analysed at 6" just before the multiphonic establishes itself shows the formation of sideband frequencies at around 43Hz spacing on either side of the initial Bb's harmonics, with a clear correspondence to the harmonic series based on the Gb trombone tube. The frequencies indicated ¶ in **Table 2** generally define the *lowest* frequency of the bandwidth of frequencies formed around the harmonics of the Bb, and although possessing relatively weak amplitude strengths at this precise point, rapidly become prominent components of the multiphonic as it stabilises. A disadvantage of this *Hypersignal* spectrographic analysis is that the frequency resolution is only accurate to *c.* 10Hz. To obtain a more precise frequency analysis a further analysis was undertaken using the *Audiosculpt* software from IRCAM.

- (c) *Audiosculpt* analysis of multiphonic 1

Table 3 and **graphs 3a-c** show the spectrum of the multiphonic itself. The analyses confirm the findings of the first analysis (a): a family of harmonics with the first four absent over a 'new' fundamental of 38.27Hz (an *1/8-tone* lower than Eb). These three

analyses show the multiphonic stabilising during time (as can clearly be seen in the spectrographic analysis **(b)**). However, the small microtonal deviations of frequency which many of the components exhibit appears to suggest that the multiphonic is comprised of two competing ‘background’ spectrums: (i) the harmonic series formed upon the ‘new’ fundamental which is the result of the characteristic interval **I**, and (ii) the harmonic series of the trombone tube itself excited by the lip and mouthpiece frequency. It appears from these analyses that the characteristic interval does not achieve its final form immediately:

the analysis 2.14” into the multiphonic shows $(233.5 - 193.1) = 40.4\text{Hz}$

“ “ 2.64” “ “ $(232.3 - 193.5) = 38.8\text{Hz}$

“ “ 3.35” “ “ $(232.3 - 193.6) = 38.7\text{Hz}$

analysis **(a)** shows: $(231.073 - 190.549) = 40.524\text{Hz}$

analysis **(b)** shows: $(236.9 - 193.8) = 43.1\text{Hz}$

Even allowing for discrepancies arising from the frequency resolution of the different analyses, it seems reasonable to conclude that the microtonal deviation of certain of the frequencies in the multiphonic (from the intonation expected of partials of an $E_b \downarrow$ fundamental) can be accounted for by looking at the harmonic series of the Gb trombone tube and the *formant characteristics*¹⁰ of the instrument.

This particular multiphonic, being formed between the 5th and 4th partials, is one of the highest practically possible multiphonics. It produces a transparent ‘harmonic’ sound which has retained its identity in the various analyses of different performances described here. The chords below are the harmonies produced by the partials of the multiphonic with consistently the strongest amplitudes (**example 3**):

example 3

Audiosculpt analyses

8" 8.5" 9.21"

analysis (a)

$\frac{\pi}{\sigma}$

Detailed description: The image shows a musical score for piano with two systems. The first system contains three measures, and the second system contains one measure. The music is written in G major and 4/4 time. The first measure of the first system is annotated with '8\"', the second with '8.5\"', and the third with '9.21\"'. Dashed lines connect these time markers to specific notes in the score. In the third measure, dashed lines connect the time marker '9.21\"' to notes with frequency numbers 27, 22, 16, 13, 10, 6, and 5. Below the first measure, there is a mathematical expression $\frac{\pi}{\sigma}$ with a horizontal line above it. The second system, labeled 'analysis (a)', shows a single measure with a similar annotation.

Table 1

frequency (Hz)	dB	relative amplitude	partial rank (of 38.27Hz fundamental)
190.549	37.48	1.0000	5
231.073	35.19	0.7682	6
271.560	23.12	0.1914	7
311.941	18.79	0.1163	8
352.360	8.95	0.0375	9
381.104	29.84	0.4150	10
431.086	11.64	0.0511	11
461.997	24.99	0.2374	12
502.629	29.72	0.4093	13
543.180	26.45	0.2809	14
571.127	25.68	0.2570	15
612.000	34.39	0.7006	16
652.707	23.36	0.1968	17
690.977			18
733.557	24.59	0.2267	19
763.056	19.67	0.1287	20
802.433	29.19	0.3850	21
843.004	33.32	0.6194	22
883.662	24.52	0.2249	23
*			24
952.962	16.15	0.0858	25
993.025	29.27	0.3886	26
1033.552	32.72	0.5781	27
*			28
1114.688	21.49	0.1587	29
			30
1183.239	20.29	0.1382	31
1223.574	26.26	0.2748	32
1264.205	17.78	0.1035	33
1304.945	18.12	0.1076	34
1332.803	12.45	0.0560	35
1373.826	18.45	0.1118	36
1413.869	24.06	0.2133	37
1454.928	21.93	0.1669	38
			39
1535.409	5.62	0.0255	40
			41
1604.709	15.04	0.0755	42
1645.659	14.51	0.0710	43
1687.298	1.04	0.0151	44
1725.747	3.9	0.0209	45
1754.550	4.17	0.0216	46
1795.130	7.61	0.0321	47
1834.862	6.22	0.0274	48

(*) data 'missing' for partials 24, 28 etc. (i.e. these partials are present in the multiphonic)

Graphs 1a, 1b : trombone multiphonic 1 analysis (i) 48ms sample

SPECTROGRAPHIC ANALYSIS

-5.000 dB/COLOR, CONTOUR ON

Time spanned: 0.000-25.22 S

FREQUENCY, LOG2
86.13 Hz 22.05 KHz

C,6,L,B:

Hydrogen (gms)

File1: sm733m
Fs: 44.10 KHz, Win: Hamm

FFT Length: 4096
Overlap: 2048
Framesize: 4096

F1 HEL
F2 PROJ
U LNOT
Fgls S
D LNH

Table 2 Trombone multiphonic 1 - spectrographic analysis 2 (6'' into sound)

Hz	relative amplitude (*)	frequency difference below(-)/above (+) Bb and harmonics	Bb	Gb fundamental of trombone tube in slide position V (Hz)	
				46.249	1
				92.498	2
				138.747	3
¶ 193.8	0.192637	-43.1	1	184.996	4
¶ 236.9	0.334760			231.245	5
279.9	0.063356	(+)43		277.494	6
323	0.017295	(+)43.1		323.743	7
¶ 376.8	0.038527	-86.2 (-43.1, -43.1)			369.992
419.9	0.130137	-43.1	2	416.241	9
463	0.549486			462.490	10
¶ 506	0.360103	(+)43		508.739	11
549.1	0.032534	(+)43.1		554.988	12
¶ 613.7	0.033390	-86.1 (43)			601.237
656.8	0.094520	-43	3	647.486	14
699.8	0.213185			693.735	15
742.9	0.101027	(+)43.1		739.984	16
786	0.050514	+86.2 (+43)		786.233	17
¶ 850.6	0.054795	-75.3			832.482
882.9	0.058219	-43	4	878.731	19
925.9	0.045377			924.980	20
969	0.054795	(+)43.1		971.229	21
¶ 1034	0.061644	-129 (-43)			1017.478
1077	0.071918	-86 (-43)	5	1063.727	23
1120	0.051370	-43		1109.976	24
1163	0.017123			1156.225	25
1206	0.023973	(+)43		1202.474	26
¶ 1227	0.020548	-173(-43,-43,-43,-43)			1248.723
1270	0.061644	-130 (-43,-43,-43)	6	1294.972	28
1314	0.063356	-86 (-43,-43)		1341.221	29
1357	0.023973	-43		1387.470	30
1400	0.035959			1433.719	31
¶ 1464	0.017123				
1497	0.016267	-129(-43,-43,-43)		1526.217	33
1540	0.011130	-86 (-43,-43)		1572.466	34
1604	0.007705	-22		1618.715	35
1626	0.025685		7		

(*) The relative amplitudes shown here are given values relative to the strongest amplitude in spectrographic analysis 1 at 1'' where the 2nd harmonic of the 'normal' Bb was given the maximum value of 1.

If, in this spectrum at 6'', the 2nd Bb harmonic (463Hz) is given the maximum value 1 then the other frequencies in the spectrum would have relatively higher values (e.g. 699.8Hz 0.38797). ¶ These frequencies are to emerge as the strongest components of the multiphonic a few seconds later.

Graphs 2a, 2b

2a

trombone multiphonic 1 spectrographic analysis 1 - 1" into sound

2b

trombone multiphonic 1 spectrographic analysis 2 - 6" into sound

Spectral Analysis and Composition

Paul Keenan

41	1573.7	-14.3	0.043652	1567.2	-20.3	0.021878			
42			0.054954	1609.7	-11.3	0.061660			
43			0.027540	1652.2	-11.3	0.061660	1645.7	-10.3	0.069183
44							1689.3	-11.3	0.061660
45			0.012162	1732.9	-20.3	0.021878			
46									
47			0.013646						
48									
49/50			0.008601						
51									
...									
...									
64									
65				2497.8	-22.4				
...									
...									
79				3027.0	-25.4	0.012162			

(*) The absence of data for many of the partials in the analysis at 9.21^{ss} does not mean to imply these partials are not present in the multiphonic. In this analysis data was obtained for the most significant partials only.

Graph 3a

3b

3c

1.2 Analysis: Trombone multiphonic 2

ex. 4

The image shows musical notation for Trombone multiphonic 2. It is divided into two sections: 'played' and 'multiphonic'.
 In the 'played' section, a bass clef staff shows a note with a dashed line above it labeled '4th partial'. Below the staff, a diagram shows a trombone mouthpiece with a finger in the first position, labeled 'VI'. A label '3rd partial' is placed between the two sections.
 In the 'multiphonic' section, the staff shows a note with a bracket above it labeled 'characteristic interval I'. Below the staff, a diagram shows a trombone mouthpiece with a finger in the first position, labeled 'new' fundamental'. Above this diagram, labels '5th partial' and '4th partial' are shown. The 'new' fundamental is marked with a flat symbol (b) and a circled note.

In comparison to multiphonic 1, multiphonic 2 is formed between lower partials and forms a denser sound with many prominent partials. Two different performances were analysed:

- (a) *Hypersignal* spectrographic analysis
- (b) FFT analysis made at the Physics Dept., University of Edinburgh¹¹.

We shall look at (a) first, a spectrographic analysis of a performance starting on F natural as the 4th partial of the tube moving into the multiphonic and stopping (without returning to the F natural 'normal' tone): see **spectrograph 'paul'**.

The general performance dynamic is *mf*. The 'time spanned' on top right of the picture is not 30.14", but 15.07" with each horizontal division therefore 1.507".

Eight spectrum analyses were made tracing the development of the sound:

- 0.72" This is 0.395" after the attack of the sound and the *1/8-tone flat* F-natural with the first eight harmonics visible in the spectrograph. (The trombonist starts on an *1/8-tone flat* F-natural in the recording). [see **graph 4a**].
- 2.3684" into the sound. The 'bending' downwards of the *1/8-tone flat* F-natural can be seen in the lowering of the harmonics. The formation of sideband frequencies is just beginning at this stage though their amplitude strengths are very weak. However, by analysis (iii) at 3.1114" sideband frequencies have increased significantly in strength and the multiphonic appears. Again, as with multiphonic 1, the intonation of the partials indicates the interaction

between the spectrum formed on the 'new' fundamental and the resonance of the trombone tube itself (see **graphs 4b,4c**).

ex. 5

The image shows musical notation for Example 5. It consists of two staves, a treble clef staff on top and a bass clef staff on the bottom. On the left, a large brace groups both staves, and the text 'harmonic series of trombone tube' is written below the bass staff. The notation includes various notes, stems, and beams, with some notes marked with '+' signs. On the right, two specific points are labeled '(i)' and '(ii)'. Below these labels, the text 'lip frequency' and ''normal' tone' is written. A dashed line connects the notes in (i) and (ii) across the two staves.

The evolution of the multiphonic can be seen in **graphs 4d-g** derived from analyses (iv)-(vii). The [Acorn] graphs only indicate up to the 33rd partial, though of course higher partials are present too. Of interest is the disappearance of the 12th partial of the D_b (which is strictly an $1/8$ -tone flatter than D_b), 409.1 Hz, in favour of a strong 13th (441.1 Hz), and the frequency 'banding' of partials 4-11, 13-20, 22-29, 30(31) - .

It would appear from a simple comparison of the harmonic series formed on the $1/8$ -tone flat F-natural and the $1/8$ -tone flatter D_b that the first components of the multiphonic spectrum arise from the reinforcement of those partials of the 'new' fundamental which most closely correspond to partials in the resonance of the trombone tube and the formant character of the instrument itself. Hence, for example, the 'missing' 12th partial of the 'new' fundamental, mentioned earlier, is not really missing because the multiphonic is not simply a harmonic series formed on the $1/8$ -tone flatter D_b . As can be seen below (**example 6**), at the point in question the multiphonic frequencies arising from the 'new' $1/8$ -tone flatter D_b fundamental that *speak* find reinforcement from the resonance of the trombone tube harmonics: the 12th harmonic, an $1/8$ -tone flatter A_b , finds itself isolated without resonance and does not sound.

ex. 6

The image displays four systems of musical notation for piano accompaniment. Each system consists of a grand staff (treble and bass clefs).
 - System 1: Labeled 'Harmonic series on F ♯'. It shows a series of notes in both hands, with a downward arrow pointing to a specific note in the treble clef.
 - System 2: Labeled 'Harmonic series on 'new' fundamental D ♭'. It shows a series of notes, with a circled note in the treble clef and a downward arrow pointing to it.
 - System 3: Labeled 'spectrograph analysis vii'. It shows notes with a circled note in the bass clef marked with (*).
 - System 4: Labeled 'spectrograph analysis v'. It shows notes with a circled note in the bass clef marked with (**).
 Dashed lines connect notes across systems, indicating relationships between the different analyses.

(*) Unfortunately, due to the frequency resolution of the FFT of the spectrograph being limited to 10Hz bands it is not possible to be completely accurate about the frequency of this crucial component. In view of the spectrum formed it seems more likely that the C ♯ indicated here is actually D ♭ (which is audible).
 (**) In analyses iii, iv and viii this is D ♯

Similarly, the other components of the 1/8-tone flatter Db harmonic series finding weak reinforcement from the '1/8-tone flat F-natural' harmonic series possess somewhat weaker amplitudes (e.g. partials 7 and 8 of the '1/8-tone flatter Db' series).

A final analysis was made of the spectrum very near to the end of the multiphonic (analysis viii, 13.96" into the sound). The 'raw' data is given in **Table 4**.

1.2.1 Trombone multiphonic and Frequency Modulation

Before continuing the discussion of multiphonic 2 with the findings of analysis (b) - an analysis of a different performance - it is appropriate here to examine the relationship between the trombone multiphonic and frequency modulation (FM)¹². It may indeed seem surprising not to have referred to FM already, but the importance of establishing the rôle of the resonance reinforcement between the harmonic series of the trombone tube itself and the 'new' fundamental's harmonic series is potentially in danger of being overlooked by the strong case for viewing the multiphonic as simply FM

Familiarity with the basic idea of frequency modulation is assumed. In electronic music the *carrier* frequency (c) would (usually) be a sine wave. The c/m ratio of 5/1 is a member of a group of ratios such that: $c/m = N_1 / N_2$ (N integers) and $f_0 = c / N_1 = m / N_2$ (where f_0 is the fundamental frequency of the modulated wave). In frequency modulation these ratios result in harmonic spectra, with the carrier frequency always the N_1 th harmonic in the series and where $N_2 = 1$ (as here), the fundamental is at the modulating frequency.

ex. 7

The appearance of the side frequencies and their position in the harmonic series can be predicted from the following (Chowning 1973):

$$k = N_1 \pm nN_2 \quad n = 0, 1, 2, 3, \dots \quad \text{where } k = \text{harmonic rank number and } n = \text{order side frequencies (} n = 0 \text{ is the carrier, } n = 1, 2, 3, \dots \text{ give two values for } k \text{ representing the harmonic rank numbers of the 1st pair - upper/lower side frequencies, 2nd pair etc.)}$$

Provided that the ratio of c/m is precisely 5/1 side frequencies will form in the following manner (see ex. 8):

ex. 8

$k = 5, n = 0$
 $k = 6,4, n = 1$
 $k = 7,3, n = 2$
 $k = 8,2, n = 3$
 $k = 9,1, n = 4$
 $k = 10,0, n = 5$
 $k = 11,1^{(*)}, n = 6$
 $k = 12,2, n = 7$
 $k = 13,3, n = 8$

(*) As can be seen in the graph below, negative frequencies 'reflect' back into the positive domain. So, for example, the -1 (-34.46Hz) becomes +1 (+34.46Hz). A particular strength of the FM technique is the spectral enrichment caused by 'reflected' frequencies.

There are several important differences between a trombone carrier frequency and the simple sine wave examples given:

- (i) The trombone F [172.3 Hz] becomes a carrier frequency which includes harmonics - each of which is also modulated. (see spectrographic analysis [i])
- (ii) It is quite unlikely that the c/m ratio will be precisely 5/1. Even a small deviation from this ratio will have significant effects (especially to the perceived stability of the modulating frequency itself). In combination with (i) above, the multiphonic produces a much more complex *inharmonic* spectrum than the linear harmonicity implied by the sine-wave FM model. (To simulate multiphonic 1 using the FM model with a single sine-wave carrier only, a high modulation index of 26-47 is required. The aural result matches the spectrum density of the multiphonic, but lacks the vitality and energy of the acoustic original).
- (iii) The trombone multiphonic will not contain the first components of the frequency modulation. This has already been explained earlier in this paper.
- (iv) In the introduction to John Chowning's article¹³ he states:

"The number of side frequencies which occur is related to the modulation index in such a way that as I^{14} increases from 0, energy is 'stolen' from the carrier and distributed among an increasing number of side frequencies."

It is clear from the spectrographic analyses of multiphonics 1 and 2 that the carrier frequency does not lose energy in the frequency modulations involved here (in multiphonic 2 the carrier appears to gaining energy!).

Looking at (i) and (ii) above in more detail provides an indication that small details combine to produce significant effects. The spectrographic analysis ii of multiphonic 2 indicated not

only the commencement of side frequencies, but also the lower intonation of the harmonics of the ‘ $\frac{1}{8}$ -tone flat F-natural’ (see graph 4b, ex. 5 and the spectrographic printout ‘paul’).

By 2.3684” (analysis ii) the spectral analysis reveals the 2nd harmonic of the ‘normal’ tone ‘ $\frac{1}{8}$ -tone flat F-natural’ (172.3 Hz) to have fallen from 344.5 Hz to 333.8 Hz (‘ $\frac{1}{8}$ -tone flat F-natural’ falling to ‘ $\frac{1}{8}$ -tone sharp E-natural’); the 3rd harmonic 516.8 Hz falling to 506 Hz (‘ $\frac{1}{8}$ -tone flat C-natural’ falling to $\frac{1}{4}$ -tone sharp B), etc.. Accepting the limitations of the analysis frequency resolution, there is non-the-less an audible lowering of frequency. Each of these harmonics contribute to the frequency modulation. If they are exact harmonic multiples of the carrier frequency their side frequencies will simply duplicate the same harmonic series as the carrier, reinforcing certain harmonics and weakening others:

ex. 9

$$2c/m = 10/11$$

$2c \pm m$ $2c \pm 2m$ $2c \pm 3m$ etc.

The musical notation for ex. 9 consists of a single staff with a treble clef and a key signature of one flat (B-flat). The notes are: B-flat (11), A-flat (9), B-flat (12), A-flat (8), B-flat (13), G-flat (7), A-flat (14), F-flat (6), G-flat (15), and E-flat (5). Brackets above the notes group them into intervals: $2c \pm m$ (between 11 and 12), $2c \pm 2m$ (between 12 and 13), $2c \pm 3m$ (between 13 and 14), and 'etc.' (between 14 and 15). Below the staff, there are three horizontal lines and a bass clef.

However, if the harmonics are not exact multiples of the carrier (as is the case here), then their contribution to the frequency modulation will be less harmonic:

ex. 10

2nd harmonic
 $333.8/m = 9.6866$

$333.8 \pm m$ $\pm 2m$ $\pm 3m$ $\pm 4m$ $\pm 5m$ etc.

The musical notation for ex. 10 consists of a single staff with a treble clef and a key signature of one flat (B-flat). The notes are: B-flat (11), A-flat (9), B-flat (12), A-flat (8), B-flat (13), G-flat (7), A-flat (15), F-flat (6), G-flat (16), and E-flat (5). Brackets above the notes group them into intervals: $333.8 \pm m$ (between 11 and 12), $\pm 2m$ (between 12 and 13), $\pm 3m$ (between 13 and 14), $\pm 4m$ (between 14 and 15), and $\pm 5m$ (between 15 and 16). Below the staff, there are three horizontal lines and a bass clef.

3rd harmonic
 $506 \pm m$ $506 \pm 2m$ $506 \pm 3m$ $506 \pm 4m$ $506 \pm 5m$

The musical notation for ex. 10 (continued) consists of a single staff with a treble clef and a key signature of one flat (B-flat). The notes are: B-flat (506), A-flat (506), B-flat (506), A-flat (506), B-flat (506), G-flat (506), A-flat (506), F-flat (506), G-flat (506), and E-flat (506). Brackets above the notes group them into intervals: $506 \pm m$ (between 506 and 506), $506 \pm 2m$ (between 506 and 506), $506 \pm 3m$ (between 506 and 506), $506 \pm 4m$ (between 506 and 506), and $506 \pm 5m$ (between 506 and 506). Below the staff, there are three horizontal lines and a bass clef.

Even though the amplitudes of the newly emerging side frequencies are very weak in analysis

(ii), the analysis supports the above argument well. (See **Table 5**)

1.2.2 Trombone multiphonic 2, 2nd performance - analysis (b)

It has been suggested in the preceding section that the linear harmonicity of the frequency modulation with c/m ratio of 5/1 becomes more complex due to the presence of harmonics which are not necessarily exactly $2c, 3c, 4c, \dots$. Also, that the c/m ratio is unlikely to be precisely 5/1. The analysis of the 2nd performance of multiphonic 2, analysis (b), yields a spectrum that strikingly demonstrates the effect of these microtonal deviations. The analysis is taken deep in the multiphonic with a frequency resolution of 3.9 Hz and reveals the presence of several additional side frequencies other than those of a harmonic series only (indicated in **graph 5** by indications such as 22a, 22b for partials close to the 22nd partial).

A second analysis of the same performance with a frequency resolution of 1.95 Hz shows so many 'additional' partials to a series formed over a Db fundamental, that it appears more useful to describe the multiphonic as a family of harmonics at a spacing of 19.19Hz with the first 6 absent, then 7,9,11 and 12-100! A study of **Table 6** shows that the partials with the stronger amplitudes tend to correspond to components of the Db modulating frequency, with the other partials appearing as further side frequencies usually with weaker amplitudes (see **Table 6** and **graph 6**).

Multiphonic 2 is a complex sound to listen to, less transparent than multiphonic 1, but rich in detail.

SPECTROGRAPHIC ANALYSIS

-5.500 dB/COLOR, CONTOUR ON Time spanned: 0.000-30.14 S

C, G, L, B: V +

File1: paul
FFT Length: 4096
Overlap: 2048
Framesize: 4096
Fs: 44.10 KHz, Win: Hamm

Graphs 4a, 4b, 4c

graph 4b, 4c

Graphs 4d-g

trombone multiphonic 2 spectrographic analyses

Trombone multiphonic 2; performance 1

Table 4

Trombone multiphonic 2 - spectrographic analysis viii 13.9549" into sound		
Frequency (Hz)	Linear amplitude	relative amplitude (1 = 220)
129.2	140.8	0.640000
172.3	202.5	0.920455
204.6	55.42	0.251909
247.6	31.92	0.145091
279.9	reading not taken at time of analysis!	
301.5	“ “ “ “ “	“ “
344.5	“ “ “ “ “	“ “
376.8	56.99	0.259045
441.8	134.70	0.612273
473.7	62.89	0.285864
516.8	60.78	0.276273
549.1	28.75	0.130682
570.6	64.16	0.291636
602.9	100.50	0.456818
646	34.66	0.157545
689.1	45.86	0.208455
742.9	59.62	0.271000
775.2	28.71	0.130500
829	29.38	0.133545
872.9	57.00	0.259090
915.2	44.71	0.203227
936.7	14.86	0.067545
1001.0	12.79	0.058136
1044.0	18.61	0.084591
1120.0	9.04	0.041109
1174.0	12.04	0.054727
1217.0	10.93	0.049682
1249.0	3.89	0.017695
1314.0	10.94	0.049727
1346.0	11.17	0.050773
...		
...		
1615.0	3.53	0.016050
1658.0	2.55	0.011577
...		
1787.0	2.53	0.011505
...		

Table 5 Trombone multiphonic 2 spectrographic analysis (ii) 2.3684"

Frequency (Hz)	linear amplitude	relative amplitude (1 = 220)
129.2	2.2570	0.010260
172.3	95.5300	0.434227
204.6	1.7510	0.007959
236.9	1.9540	0.008882
258.4	1.6500	
301.5	2.4660	
333.8	95.1600	0.432545
409.1	0.9406	
430.7	0.5933	
452.2	1.9680	
¶ 506	115.4000	0.524545
538.1	3.4100	0.015500
559.9	2.1560	
592.2	2.1710	
646	1.7800	
¶ 678.3	15.0100	0.068227
721.4	0.4920	
764.4	1.5770	
807.5	2.4600	
839.8	20.6200	0.093727
882.9	0.7814	
936.7	1.2590	
979.8	1.2730	
1012.0	8.0600	0.036636
1044.0	0.6801	
1077.0	0.3907	
1098.0	0.3184	
1120.0	0.4486	
1174.0	3.4730	
1249.0	0.2026	
1346.0	1.5050	

Graph 5: Trombone multiphonic 2, performance 2, analysis 1

Table 6

trombone
multiphonic 2,
performance
2, analysis 2

freq (Hz)	dB	relative amplitude	partial rank 19.19Hz=1	partial rank 34Hz = 1	freq.(Hz) (n * 34)
49.32	-1.96	0.025971			
72.3	-7.4	0.013883	4		
98.27	-14.78	0.005936	5		
			6		
134.49	11.06	0.116279	7	4	
149.96	-12.33	0.00787	8		
172.92	26.69	0.703072	9	5	
			10		
210.81	18.92	0.287409	11	6	
231.2	-7.13	0.014321	12	7	
249.76	-2.11	0.025527	13		
269.02	11.86	0.127497	14	8	
287.57	8.1	0.082699	15		
306.84	12.13	0.131522	16	9	
325.05	3.74	0.050061	17		
346.07	14.55	0.17378	18	10	
363.45	-0.71	0.029991	19		
383.83	24.47	0.544503	20	11	
403.8	14.14	0.165768	21	12	
423.06	9.51	0.097274	22		
441.81	29.75	1	23	13	
459.84	16.31	0.212814	24	14	
480.72	14.97	0.18239	25		
498.35	14.05	0.164059	26	15	
518.13	5.67	0.062517	27		
538.21	11.19	0.118032	28	16	
556.29	13.72	0.157943	29		
576.03	22.67	0.442588	30	17	
594.47	15.87	0.202302	31		
614.73	25.83	0.636796	32	18	
632.52	17.77	0.251768	33	19	
653.43	14.61	0.174985	34	19	646
671.26	17.64	0.248028	35	20	680
690.66	15.62	0.196562	36		
710.5	21.35	0.380189	37	21	
729.23	18.78	0.282813	38		
749.22	19.96	0.323966	39	22	
766.89	6.25	0.066834	40		
787.36	9.49	0.097051	41	23	
805.11	9.6	0.098287	42		
825.59	17.84	0.253805	43	24	816
845.24	12.27	0.13366	44	25	
865.37	18	0.258523	45		
883.16	25.06	0.582774	46	26	
902.62	17.1	0.233077	47		

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922.84	17.72	0.250323	48	27	918
			49		
960.66	16.57	0.21928	50	28	952
979.37	14.36	0.17002	51		
999.22	10.94	0.114683	52		
1017.98	21.51	0.387258	53	30	1020
1033.89	9.58	0.098061	54		
1056.36	21.24	0.375405	55	31	
1076.06	4.51	0.054701	56		
1096.45	12.89	0.143549	57	32	1088
1114.61	11.29	0.119399	58	33	1122
1134.08	9.43	0.096382	59		
1151.97	13.68	0.157217	60	34	1156
1171.49	10.29	0.106414	61		
1190.26	11.02	0.115744	62	35	1190
1210.7	3.36	0.047918	63		
1230.14	9.03	0.092045	64	36	1224
1246.29	-4.7	0.018945	65		
1267.97	9.01	0.091833	66	37	1258
1286.82	9.61	0.098401	67	38	1292
1307.14	9.62	0.098514	68		
1324.83	11.46	0.121759	69	39	1326
1344.61	5.76	0.063168	70		
1363.95	9	0.091727	71	40	1360
1382.28	2.6	0.043903	72	41	1394
1400.87			73		
1421.06	0.34	0.033845	74	42	
1441.7	4.14	0.05242	75		
1459.42	8.44	0.086	76	43	
1479	-3.12	0.022724	77		
1497.57	1.2	0.037368	78	44	
1517.19	-1.3	0.028022	79	45	1530
			80		
1555.02	-10.41	0.009817	81		
1575.53	-3.78	0.021062	82	46	1564
1594.27	-2.57	0.02421	83	47	
1614.09	-9.31	0.011142	84		
1631.97	-6.66	0.015118	85	48	
1651.55	-10.59	0.009616	86		
1672.3	-7.32	0.014012	87	49	
			88		
			89		
1727.33	-11.07	0.009099	90	51	1734
			91		
1766.31	-14.82	0.005908	92	52	
			93		
			94		
			95		
			96		
1860.58	-16.51	0.004864	97	55	1870
			98		
1907.05	-12.7	0.007542	99	56	1904
			100		
1948.42	-19.79	0.003334	101	57	1938
			102		

Graph 6: Trombone multiphonic 2, performance 2, analysis 2

1.3 Trombone multiphonic 3

Multiphonic 3 is formed by playing Eb [155.56Hz] as the 3rd partial of the fundamental Ab (position III) and ‘bending’ down towards the 2nd partial Ab:

ex.11

The image shows two musical staves in bass clef. The first staff, labeled 'played', shows a note Eb on the third line with a '3' above it and a '2' below it, indicating the 3rd and 2nd partials. Below the staff is a fingering 'III' and a dynamic marking 'f'. The second staff, labeled 'expected multiphonic(*)', shows a note Eb on the third line with a '4' above it and a '3' below it, indicating the 4th and 3rd partials. Below the staff is a fingering 'I' and a dynamic marking 'new' f'. A note below the staff is labeled 'new' f. A footnote (*) says 'Following the report by Castellengo et al..'

Analyses were made of 3 performances:

- **3.1** A 48ms sample of the multiphonic at a frequency resolution of 3.9Hz¹⁵.
- **3.2** Spectrographic analyses of the formation, multiphonic, and return to the ‘normal’ tone as performed in the example above (i.e. ‘bending’ down of the initial ‘normal’ tone).
- **3.3** Spectrographic analyses of the formation and multiphonic produced by starting on the Ab 2nd partial and ‘bending’ up towards the Eb 3rd partial.

Being formed between the low partials 2 and 3, a fifth apart, the ‘lowering’ of lip frequency involved in forming the multiphonic in 3.1 and 3.2 appears in these analyses to diverge from the *expected* new fundamental/modulating frequency:

ex. 12

The image shows three musical staves in bass clef. The first staff, labeled 'ex. 12', shows a note Eb on the third line with a '3' above it and a '2' below it, indicating the 3rd and 2nd partials. Below the staff is a fingering 'III' and a dynamic marking 'f'. The second staff, labeled '3.1', shows a note Eb on the third line with a '4' above it and a '3' below it, indicating the 4th and 3rd partials. Below the staff is a fingering 'I' and a dynamic marking 'new' f. A note below the staff is labeled 'new' f and has a frequency of 37.075 Hz. The third staff, labeled '3.2', shows a note Eb on the third line with a '4' above it and a '3' below it, indicating the 4th and 3rd partials. Below the staff is a fingering 'I' and a dynamic marking 'new' f. A note below the staff is labeled 'new' f.

Analysis **3.1** (see **Table 7** and **graphs 7**) reveals a spectrum with a family of harmonics at 37.075Hz spacing with the first 2 components missing. The intonation of the partials accords well with a frequency modulation where $c/m = 4/1 = 149.463/37.075$. However, as can be

seen, the strengths of the partials is fairly equally high (particularly clear in the logarithmic graph display of relative amplitude strengths) and the resulting sound does not sound harmonic - as would seem to be implied by the spectrum's harmonic series structure.

Analysis 3.2 (see spectrograph "sm635", tables 8a-d and graphs 8a-d) confirms the general structure of harmonics of 3.1 but the precise intonation of the frequencies is less exactly in correspondence with the FM of $c/m = 4/1$. These deviations of intonation have been discussed earlier with similarities here to multiphonic 2.

It is clear to see in the example below (example 13) how the lowest components of 3.2 are, in a sense, a *compromise* between the lowest partials of the 2 harmonic series: (i) The Ab trombone tube resonance and (ii) the $c/m = 4/1$ frequency modulation.

ex. 13

The image displays a musical score for Example 13, consisting of four staves. The top two staves are labeled "3.2 analysis iii" and "3.2 analysis iv". The bottom two staves are labeled "'new' fundamental/ modulating frequency 37.7 Hz" and "harmonic series of Ab trombone tube".

The score is written in bass clef for the left hand and treble clef for the right hand. The key signature has one sharp (F#). The time signature is not explicitly shown but appears to be common time (C).

Key numerical values and labels are as follows:

- 3.2 analysis iii:** Frequencies 193.8, 258, 398.4, 409.1, 419.9 are indicated above the notes.
- 3.2 analysis iv:** Shows a similar melodic line with different intonation.
- 'new' fundamental/ modulating frequency 37.7 Hz:** A series of notes starting from a low frequency, with partials numbered 1 through 18.
- harmonic series of Ab trombone tube:** A series of notes starting from a low frequency, with partials numbered 2 through 13.

Dashed lines connect the notes in the analyses to the corresponding partials in the harmonic series, illustrating the relationship between the two.

Analysis **3.3** is of interest in showing that essentially the same multiphonic results as 3.2, but here it is formed by starting on the Ab 2nd partial and ‘bending’ *upwards* towards the Eb 3rd partial. The significance of this lies in questioning the statement made by Castellengo et al. (1983)¹⁶: “*En montant la fréquence du partial n, on passe au partiel supérieur sans qu’il y ait production de ce multiphonique.*” [“When one raises the frequency of partial **n** one passes to the next higher partial without the production of this multiphonic.”]

The glissando-like ‘bending’ upwards towards the Eb 3rd partial is clearly visible in **spectrograph “mm635b”**. The graphs of analyses i-iv cover the period from the attack of the sound to just before the multiphonic appears (see **graphs 9a-d**). Analysis v (**graph 9e**) is taken just at the start of the multiphonic, which presents a ‘wall’ of sound with partials *c.*10.8Hz apart! It is worth noting however, that the partials with strongest amplitudes tend to be at frequencies at, or close to, resonance points of the trombone tube itself (which is in the Ab position). Later in the multiphonic the frequencies 366.1Hz and 409.1Hz emerge strongly, around the 7th and 8th partials of the trombone tube fundamental. A comparison with 3.2 suggests that 3.3 is essentially the same multiphonic, but the increased volume of it’s performance (3.2 is performed quite quietly) contributes to the increased number of additional side frequencies.

There remains much spectral analytical work to be done to be certain that the same trombone multiphonic can be achieved whether formed from ‘above’ or ‘below’.

Table 7 Trombone multiphonic 3.1

freq (Hz)	dB	relative amplitude	partial rank f=37.075Hz	harmonic series of Ab
				51.91
110.66	9.97	0.181134	3	103.83
149.46	16.42	0.380627	4	155.74
189.03	13.19	0.262422	5	207.65
223.2	17.42	0.427071	6	259.57
259.89	20.82	0.631684	7	311.48
298.04	10.66	0.196110	8	363.39
336.72	19.24	0.526623	9	415.3
371.97	19.37	0.534564	10	467.22
409.28	19.88	0.566892	11	519.13
446.96	22.29	0.748170	12	571.04
481.94	21.68	0.697429	13	622.96
526.97	11.75	0.222331	14	674.87
			15	726.78
592.91	22.92	0.804452	16	778.7
630.24	23.83	0.893305	17	830.61
674.11	14.42	0.302343	18	882.52
702.31	24.81	1.000000	19	934.43
740.89	19.14	0.520595	20	986.35
			21	1038.26
815.54	20.62	0.617305	22	1090.17
852.55	20.02	0.576103	23	1142.09
890.27	20.62	0.617305	24	1194
			25	1245.91
963.48	22.27	0.746449	26	1297.83
			27	1349.74
1033.59	14.27	0.297167	28	1401.65
			29	1453.56
1113.35	24.21	0.933254	30	1505.48
			31	1557.39
			32	1609.3
1223.46	21.47	0.680769	33	1661.22
1261.13	18.56	0.486968	34	1713.13
			35	1765.04
1333.57	17.99	0.456037	36	1816.95
1372.34	18.97	0.510505	37	1868.87
			38	1920.78
1443.74	14.81	0.316228	39	1972.69
1483.22	19.15	0.521195	40	
			41	
1555.51	17.51	0.431519	42	
1593.72	15.29	0.334195	43	
			44	
1665.38	12.87	0.252930	45	
1704.67	15.38	0.337676	46	
			47	
			48	
1814.58	4.5	0.096493	49	
1853.79	12.31	0.237137	50	
1890.29	10.96	0.203002	51	
1924.99	7.24	0.132282	52	
1964.24	13.3	0.265766	53	
2002	9.76	0.176807	54	
2036.66	8.64	0.155418	55	
2074.98	6.49	0.121339	56	
2112.02	3.27	0.083752	57	
2147.84	7.08	0.129867	58	

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2186.14	8.26	0.148765	59
			60
2258.81	2.74	0.078795	61
2297.13	7.04	0.129271	62
2334.71	2.81	0.079432	63
2368.73	1.17	0.065765	64
2407.42	2.79	0.079250	65
2446.01	2.08	0.073029	66
2482.43	-1.31	0.049431	67

Graph

Graphs 7a ,7b Trombone multiphonic 3.1

SPECTROGRAPHIC ANALYSIS

-5.000 dB/COLOR, CONTOUR ON

Time spanned: 0.000-30.00 S

C, G, L, B:

FFT Length: 4096
Overlap: 2048
Framesize: 4096

File1: sm635
Fs: 44.10 KHz, Win: Hamm

F1 HEL
F2 PRG
U UNOT
PgUp S
D DWH

Table 8a

multiphonic 3.2 analysis (i)				
freq (Hz)	linear ampl.	rel ampl	partial rank	
161.5		27.81	0.421939	1
312.2		19.25	0.292065	2
473.7		65.91	1	3
624.5		38.24	0.581702	4
786		25.1	0.380822	5
947.5		17.39	0.263845	6
1098		5.85	0.088870	7
1260		2.33	0.035397	8

Table 8b

3.2 analysis (ii)

freq. (Hz)	linear ampl.	rel. ampl.	partial rank	harmonic series of 150.7Hz
150.7	25.91	0.39	1	150.7
301.5	51.87	0.79	2	301.4
452.2	29.08	0.44	3	452.1
602.9	11.63	0.18	4	602.8
753.7	7.1	0.11	5	753.5
764.4	7.2	0.11		
872.1	2.3	0.03		
915.2	10.1	0.15	6	904.2
1066	4.6	0.07	7	1054.9
1217	2.3	0.03	8	1205.6

Table 8c

3.2 analysis (iii)

freq. (Hz)	linear ampl.	rel. ampl.	partial rank of 'new' fundamental/ modulating frequency: 37.7Hz	harmonic series of 37.7Hz (freq.)
				1 37.7
75.37	0.84	0.01	2	75.4
107.7	3.31	0.05	3	113.1
150.7	22.09	0.34	4	150.8
193.8	6.7	0.10	5	188.5
		0	6	226.2
258.4	12	0.18	7	263.9
301.5	27.6	0.42	8	301.6
344.5	7.2	0.11	9	339.3
398.4	5.5	0.08	10	377
409.1/419.9	5.5	0.08	11	414.7
452.2	7.3	0.11	12	452.4
506	11.3	0.17	13	490.1
		0	14	527.8
570.6	3.4	0.05	15	565.5
613.7	5.6	0.08	16	603.2
		0	17	640.9
678.3	9.7	0.15	18	678.6
		0	19	716.3

786	3.7	0	20	754
829	6.2	0.05	21	791.7
		0.09	22	829.4
893.6	2.5	0	23	867.1
936.7	5.5	0.03	24	904.8
		0.08	25	942.5

Graphs 8a, 8b

Graphs 8c, 8d multiphonic 3.2

analysis iii 8.5" (start of multiphonic)

analysis iv 15.56" (just over half-way into multiphonic)

relative amplitude

Graphs 9a-d multiphonic 3.3

trombone multph 3.3

Graph 9e multiphonic 3.3 analysis (v)

(*) cf. multiphonic 3.1 $f=37.075$ Hz; multiphonic 3.2 $f=37.7$ Hz

In multiphonic 3.3 the spectrum shows the intonation of the partials fluctuating - e.g. partial 11a,11b where 11a = (37.075×11) and 11b = (37.7×11)

(**) Ab fundamental of trombone tube (slide position III)

Trombone Multiphonic 3.3

SPECTROGRAPHIC ANALYSIS

Time spanned: 0.000-15.37 S

-5.500 dB/COLOR, CONTOUR ON

22.05 KHz

F1 HEL
F2 F81
U INT
Page 5
D WH

C, G, L, B: V + E

File1: mm635b

FFT Length: 4096

Overlap: 2048

Framesize: 4096

Fs: 44.10 KHz, Win: Hamm

1.4 Trombone multiphonic 4

On the trombone sometimes called the ‘tenor-bass’ trombone, or Bb & F trombone, it is possible to achieve a multiphonic with fewer prominent partials - which then sound more clearly audible in a transparent ‘harmony/timbre’. As described by the trombonist¹⁷ performing the multiphonic: “*In a slightly sharpened position VI with the F valve, play a normal in-tune F-natural and slide to an out-of-tune Ab.*”

On the tenor-bass trombone the intonation of the lowest slide positions V and VI with the F valve and E.slide can be difficult to specify in terms of the more usual tenor trombone positions, but the situation is clarified by studying **example 14**. The spectrum of the multiphonic can be seen in **graph 10**.

ex. 14

The notation shows two parts: 'played' and 'multiphonic'.
 - 'played': Bass clef, quarter note G2 (5), quarter note Bb2 (6). Fingering: 2, 1. Valve: VI+.
 - 'multiphonic': Bass clef, quarter note G2 (7), quarter note Bb2 (6). Fingering: 1, 2. Valve: I. A note with a flat and a sharp symbol is labeled 'new fundamental/modulating frequency'.
 - 'FM c/m = 6/1': A note with a flat and a sharp symbol, labeled 'm'.

graph 10

The FM where $c/m = 6/1 = 178.1 / 29.683$ accords well with the prominent frequencies of multiphonic 4 (allowing for the non-sounding components). There is also a parallel with multiphonic 1, which similarly relates to an FM where $c/m = 6/1$ (see examples 15 and 16).

ex. 15

ex. 16

multiphonic 1: *multiphonic 4:*

Musical notation for multiphonic 1 and multiphonic 4. Multiphonic 1 is shown in a treble clef with a complex chord structure. Multiphonic 4 is shown in a bass clef with a similar complex chord structure. Numerical labels are placed above and below the notes to indicate specific frequencies or components.

Component	Multiphonic 1	Multiphonic 4
Top	27	31
Upper-Mid	22	25
Mid	16	19
Lower-Mid	10, 13	12, 13
Bottom	6, 5	7, 6

1.5 Conclusion

- The report by Castellengo et al. provides a useful ‘rule-of-thumb’ method for predicting the likely ‘new’ fundamental/modulating frequency and the characteristic interval **I**, though it is not always accurate. (The actual multiphonic is frequently *messier*, with significant microtonal deviations). The formulae are only valid if **n** = the higher component of **I**.
- The ‘missing’ lower components of the multiphonic can be explained by the lack of correspondence between the new spectrum and the resonance of the trombone tube itself.
- There is a definite parallel with frequency modulation (FM) spectra, though *c/m* ratios are seldom precise integers, and the carrier frequency’s harmonics will have a significant effect on the harmonicity/inharmonic of the spectrum; the amplitude strengths of the individual components within the multiphonic will also relate to the harmonic series and formant characteristics of the trombone itself.
- Multiphonics can be formed either from partial **n** ‘bending’ towards **n - 1**, or from partial **n - 1** rising towards **n** (multiphonics 3.3 and 4 show this possibility). It seems possible that a similar or the same multiphonic is formed, though further research is needed to be certain. Some further points that relate to this issue are discussed below.

ex. 17

The image shows musical notation for four different multiphonic or FM spectra. Each is represented by a staff with notes and a corresponding harmonic series below it.

- multiphonic 4**: Shows a note with a sharp sign and a note with a flat sign. The harmonic series below has a ratio of $c/m = 6/1$.
- multiphonic 3.3**: Shows a note with a flat sign and a note with a sharp sign. The harmonic series below has a ratio of $c/m = 6/1$.
- FM(a)**: Shows a note with a flat sign. The harmonic series below has a ratio of $c/m = 2.666/1$.
- FM(b)**: Shows a note with a flat sign. The harmonic series below has a ratio of $c/m = 4/1$.

Based on the FM resulting in multiphonic 4, where the multiphonic is approached from below and the initial 'normal' tone F becomes the carrier frequency in the ensuing FM (see **example 17**), it is possible to interpret the much denser multiphonic 3.3 as the product of two FM spectra. In 3.3, accepting the 38.89Hz Eb as the modulating frequency (as predicted by the report by Castellengo et al. if the multiphonic is approached from the higher partial 3 Eb [155.56Hz]), then a frequency modulation between the initial Ab of 3.3 and the 38.89Hz and a frequency modulation between the higher partial Eb (155.56Hz) and the 38.89Hz would produce a dense spectrum corresponding very well to the spectrum actually produced in multiphonic 3.3 (see **example 18**).

Ex. 18

Notes and References

The Spectral Analysis of Trombone Multiphonics

¹ “*Palimpsest*” for soprano, ensemble and computer-realised electronics. Composed by the present writer (1992-5).

² Bartolozzi, B. (1967), *New Sounds for Woodwind*, translated and edited by Reginald Smith Brindle, Oxford University Press.

³ Even a composer as precise and complex in notational matters as Brian Ferneyhough notates oboe multiphonics in “*Carceri d’Invenzione III*” (1986) in the following manner:

⁴ Castellengo, M., Caussé, R., Sluchin, B. “*Comparative study of the phenomenon of bitonality in human voice and multiphonic emissions of brass instruments*” Stockholm Music Acoustics Conference 1983.

⁵ Castellengo, M., Caussé, R., Sluchin, B. *Étude acoustique de l’émission multiphoniques aux cuivres*, 11e Congrès International d’acoustique, Paris 1983, proc. Vol.4 (355-7).

⁶ *ibid.*

⁷ All analyses presented here which are not *Hypersignal* spectrographic analyses or *Audiosculpt* analyses are analyses made by Dr Raymond Parks, Department of Physics, The University of Edinburgh. The analysis program is written by Dr Parks.

⁸ The conversion from amplitude (dB) to relative amplitude employs the formula:

$$(i) \text{ relative amplitude} = 10^{(\text{maximum dB} / 20)} = X$$

$$(ii) X / X = 1$$

For subsequent dB conversions: $x_n / X = 0 < n > 1$

⁹ The *Hypersignal* spectrographic analyses were made with the help of Dr Stephen Malloch at the Physics Dept., The University of Edinburgh.

¹⁰ Although the trombone is generally considered an instrument without marked formant characteristics of its own, the results of the various multiphonic analyses suggest a clear formant region around 440-510 Hz.

¹¹ See footnote 7 above.

¹² Chowning, J., (1973), “*The synthesis of complex audio spectra by means of frequency modulation*”, *Journal of the Audio Engineering Society* 21(7): 526-534, 1973.

¹³ *ibid.*

¹⁴ $I = \text{the modulation index} = d/m$ where $d = \text{peak deviation (of the carrier } c)$ and $m = \text{modulating frequency}$.

¹⁵ Analysis made by Dr R. Parks (see footnote 7 above)

¹⁶ See footnote 5 above. The comment “...*ce multiphonique*” has been interpreted to mean the production of this type of multiphonic (i.e. ‘lip’ multiphonics). Castellengo et al. appear to be stating that lip multiphonics cannot be formed by starting on partial n and raising to the next higher partial ($n + 1$); multiphonic 3.3 in this present study clearly contradicts this. However, it is true that the same multiphonic will not be formed by (i) ‘bending’ from partial n towards ($n - 1$) and (ii) n towards ($n + 1$).

¹⁷ Trombonist/composer John Kenny. All the trombone multiphonics analysed in this study were performed by Mr. Kenny.

2. Outline of some of the ways spectral analyses are used in the compositions

Several spectral analyses have been made of other instruments: clarinet tones and multiphonics; cor anglais; ‘cello; various gongs and tam-tams; bowed cymbal lying inverted on a pedal timpani; large empty gas cylinders; vocal tones. The results of these analyses together with the detailed analyses of trombone multiphonics presented earlier in this document, have been incorporated into most of the compositions of the Ph.D. folio in several ways:

- Harmonic and pitch material. Chords have been derived from complex spectra (such as the trombone multiphonics) by filtering or enhancing specific partials (as in *Palimpsest 3rd section*). These derived chords are included on the electroacoustic tape as well as scored for the ‘live’ acoustic instruments where account is taken of the amplitude development of the various partials. With the use of computer signal processing it has been possible to combine spectra to enhance and enrich significant ‘shared’ characteristics (for example, see page 1 of *Squaring xlvii*: at the entry of the DAT where trombone multiphonic 1 and the spectra of a bowed cymbal lying inverted on a pedal timpani combine in sharing many significant partials in a lively sound)^[1]. The notation of some of the electroacoustic material has been made to make the precise harmonic relationships between the tape and ‘live’ instrumental music clear. In any case both the electroacoustic and acoustic music often has a shared origin from the spectral analyses of the trombone multiphonics.
- The chords derived from these spectral analyses are not always treated as ‘fixed’, though the original frequencies of the significant partials are accorded a *privileged* position

within a network of relationships formed. (For example, the most significant partials of trombone multiphonic 1 - 5,6,10,13,16,22,27 - can themselves be treated as fundamentals, or accorded a different partial position within a transposition so the Eb partial 16 is considered the 27th partial of the transposed chord etc.).

- While harmonic connections between different instrumental spectra are explored and juxtaposed, the intervals (usually microtonal) between the significant partials in the trombone multiphonics, and between one multiphonic and another are deployed in the melodic/polyphonic writing. In some instances, the frequencies of a multiphonic are presented sequentially according to an ordering by amplitude strength (from strongest to weakest, or weakest to strongest, or by a function derived from another scheme...).
- Frequency bandwidths derived from the trombone multiphonics determine some aspects of the pitch material in *Comet Hale-Bopp* (in connection with other schemes occurring simultaneously which are also derived from the trombone multiphonics).
- Certain passages of *Squaring xlvii* project the microtonal and amplitude evolution of partials originating from trombone multiphonics over a longer time span as an ‘enlargement’ into the foreground. For example, the multi-tracked trombone music on pages 2-4: here detailed analyses tracing five seconds of subtle fluctuations in intonation, breath, small glissandi and amplitudes of certain frequencies contained in the spectral ‘mutating’ of trombone multiphonic 1 with the bowed cymbal referred to above, is expanded to the time span of a tam-tam decay and made audible. The particular harmony at this point being an example of the transposition of the most significant partials of multiphonic 1.
- The entire electroacoustic section which commences *Comet Hale-Bopp* is created solely from a five second edited sample of trombone multiphonic 1.

Many rhythmic and durational processes also derive from the spectral analyses. Some examples are given below:

- Structures have been created where a gradual *accelerando* is derived from various spectra through a *metaphorical* relationship formed between amplitude strength and duration. It seems a reasonable extension of imagination to posit that partials with strong, audible significance could be accorded a longer duration and weaker partials shorter durations etc. (there are many variants of this idea possible of course). Rhythmic cells can then be constructed by comparing the amplitude strength of each partial in turn from several spectra. Setting an arbitrary duration (or a duration from some other scheme) to correspond to the strongest amplitude of all the compared spectra, cells are constructed by superimposing the various durations. The spectra of ‘normal’ clarinet, cor anglais, and ‘cello tones have been used in this manner, where there are significant differences between amplitude strengths even comparing partials 1,2,3,4... . The passage commencing in the 6 flutes a bar after letter **F** in *Comet Hale-Bopp* (page 22) continuing to letter **G** illustrates this idea. Similarly, the soprano melody in *Squaring xlvii* from page 10-13.

- Two functions describing the wave shapes formed from the most significant partials of trombone multiphonic 1 and 2 have also been used:

$$(i) \quad y = \sin 5x + .77\sin 6x + .414\sin 10x + .41\sin 13x + .7\sin 16x + .62\sin 22x + .578\sin 27x$$

$$(ii) \quad y = .7031\sin 5x + .5445\sin 11x + \sin 13x + .4429\sin 17x + .6368\sin 18x + .5828\sin 26x + .3873\sin 30x$$

These functions have been used in tempo relationships in *Comet Hale-Bopp* (letter **H...**) and in other ways.

- The significant partials of trombone multiphonic 1: 5 6 10 13 16 22 27

suggest a pattern of growth similar to the well known Fibonacci series. By slightly adapting the partial number series, a version of the Fibonacci series can be seen:

Partials:	5	6	10	13	16	22	27
Fibonacci series:	3	5	8	13	21	34	
partial numbers adapted to segments of Fibonacci series	5	3 [6/2]	5 [10/2]	13	8 [16/2]	21* * partial 21 of the multiphonic is occasionally more prominent than the 22nd	[34]

These number series have been used (and others) particularly in Comet Hale-Bopp where growth and decay patterns have seemed most appropriate to the comet's approach and 'after-images' (the long receding tail).

It has not been the intention here to give a detailed account of the techniques and ideas explored in the compositions, but to give a concise indication of some of the ways in which the spectral analyses have been explored and developed. In addition to the methods outlined above, a particular concern has been an attempt to develop and integrate the use of spectra in conjunction with other (post serial) technical procedures that do not originate directly from spectra.

As an example, in part I and II of *Palimpsest* two different 'pulse-rhythms'^[2] are used as structural frameworks: 9:8 and (in part II) 6:5. As has been seen earlier, one of the features of the trombone multiphonic is the formation of a characteristic interval [I] at the bass of the perceived multiphonic, where I becomes integrated into the spectrum of a 'new' fundamental. In the case of multiphonic 1 I = partials 5 and 6 of the slightly flat Eb

fundamental/modulating frequency. If the rhythmic values of the 6:5 'pulse-rhythm' are multiplied (in this instance by 30) it is possible to make the 2nd and 3rd values of the 'pulse-rhythm' - $1/6$, $1/5$ - correspond to the 5:6 [6:5 reversed] minor 3rd. Thereafter create a 'series' of partials directly from the 'pulse-rhythm' rhythmic values:

'pulse-rhythm' values	5/6	1/6	1/5	7/15	1/3	2/5	1/10	1/2	...
partial rank	25	5	6	14	10	12	3	15	...

The interesting result of this process is that the spectrum produced is analogous to instrumental spectra, but that each 'pulse-rhythm' has its own 'characteristic harmony' (when octaves are eliminated). Clearly, if each 'pulse-rhythm' is generated from a ratio between two integer values, spectra can be constructed by considering each integer a partial rank position of the spectra ($9:8$ = major 2nd, partials 8 and 9 of a spectrum etc.).

As a sort of inverse procedure to the idea of deriving durations from the amplitude strength mentioned earlier, the duration values produced by the 'pulse-rhythm' can be used to filter out partials from (the particularly dense lower) trombone multiphonics by selecting partials with matching, or closely matching, amplitude strengths.

The possibilities are endless. Spectral analyses provide a rich resource which has been used in a *loop* or *chain* whereby analyses made of acoustic phenomena, such as trombone multiphonics, provide material for new acoustic or electroacoustic music, which latter in turn is analysed to yield further acoustic instrumental possibilities...

3. The notation of electroacoustic music

In *Palimpsest part III* most of the instrumental music was composed first, before the electroacoustic tape music. Since many spectral analyses had already been made and much of the instrumental music composed in the light of these analyses, creating precise pitch and harmonic relationships in the electroacoustic music was a high priority. Notating the electronics as accurately as possible in traditional *musical* notation enables these pitch relationships, and the dialogues between the acoustic ‘live’ ensemble and the tape to be made clear.

Where the electroacoustic music has been created by synthesis (Csound) it has been possible to make an accurate musical notation (e.g. letter C, page 59 *Palimpsest III*). The music in these places has been ‘composed’ in a similar manner to the instrumental music and is therefore relatively easy to notate in terms of pitch and rhythmic elements.

In many other places the musical notation has been achieved with the results of further spectral analyses using *Hypersignal* spectrographic analyses (and later, in parts of *Squaring xvii*, the software *Audiosculpt*). Creating a musical score from hundreds of individual 0.04644”-sized frames of spectral analyses is a very slow process! Fortunately, as can be seen in the spectrographic analyses of the trombone multiphonics, it is possible to obtain a printout of the complete ‘time-span’ of the sound analysed. With the two formats: (i) the overall picture of the sound, and (ii) analyses of individual 46-47ms samples it has been possible to provide musical notation of some of the electroacoustic music where the computer algorithms in *randomising*^[3] processes (see pages 61-68 of *Palimpsest*).

Quite aside from the time involved, there are many difficulties inherent in undertaking the task of notating. In the passage of *Palimpsest* commencing on page 61, the music is fast.

Creating a notation which corresponds to the huge amount of analysis data and also to what is *perceived* when listening (auditive analysis) requires a subtle ingenuity. Possibly, in this

passage (p.61-), more information has been notated than can be heard. Nonetheless, since the results can prove to be a new 'source' to explore in music composed for instruments, it is to be hoped that with developments in computer analysis/synthesis programs, the time will come when some form of acceptable *musical* notation can be produced at the same time as the data is processed for sound.

There are other passages (in *Palimpsest*) where the musical notation was achieved through the same process of detailed spectral analysis combined to careful listening to the sound:

- letter **A2** (page 47-). Beginning with a clarinet multiphonic/bell sound (where the clarinet multiphonic is the same as that played by the 'live' clarinetist three bars earlier (p.46)). The continuing tape music (p.48-) is constructed from a single 'cello and violin harmonics with frequencies chosen to both enhance the higher (weaker) partials of trombone multiphonic 1 being played 'live', and also relate to the string quartet chord at **A2**^[4]. The complex sharp *staccato* sounds commencing at 14.675" (p.51) continue much longer (and become much faster) than the notation indicates. All the music from page 48-51 was notated from spectral analyses combined with the knowledge of how the sound was constructed (there are no random processes involved here).
- Pages 78-83
- Pages 121-122 (end of *Palimpsest*)

The arguments for and against the notation of electroacoustic music are complex. A pragmatic view would say that it is only necessary to indicate what is important for the co-ordination of the tape with the musicians: essentially time-line information and important cues. Another view, suggested for instance by Marco Stroppa^[5], is that without the existence of a *score* as distinct from operational data or graphic representations, any deeper understanding or analysis of the electronic music as *music* is restricted and limited in

comparison to the opportunity to both hear and see the score of a piece of music for instruments (and thereby analyse and reflect upon the music outside of the performance time of the music).

The experience of attempting as thorough a notation as possible in *Palimpsest* leads to some provisional conclusions:

- The electroacoustic music in *Palimpsest* is closely related to the instrumental. To the extent that it accords a high significance to pitch, in melodic/timbral senses, it is appropriate to employ musical notation as much as possible. In these instances the notation serves both the pragmatic and idealistic functions of aiding performance synchronization and making visibly clear the shared musical connections (see **B2**, **C**, **D2**, **E**, **H2** etc.).
- The ability to achieve a fully notated score is integrally related to the means of creating the electronics. By employing spectral analyses programs it is possible to make a notation of passages not directly ‘composed’ but generated by computer algorithms, but the time involved is daunting.
- In the electroacoustic passages without instruments there is no pragmatic need to notate the music (there are no *performers*), other than to give sufficient timing and/or cuing information. On the whole, these passages have also included the use of algorithms which make the task of notation more difficult. However, an attempt has been made in all cases (see pages 61-75; **L**; **P-end**).

In *Squaring* *xlvi* and *Comet Hale-Bopp* the electroacoustic music has been notated as much as possible. It will be seen that the most exact notation has been given at points in the scores where it is most useful (e.g. pages 18-20 of *Squaring*), while at other places (e.g. p.29

Squaring) graphisms are employed. While the graphisms are appropriate representations of the 'quasi-birdsong' on p.29, the passage beginning at 1'00" should ideally be notated in much more detail. The issue here centres on the amount of time required to achieve a meaningful notation; the solution presented in the score is not satisfactory in providing much indication of what the music *sounds* like.

The interconnected relationships between spectral analyses, composing, electroacoustic music, notational problems, further analysis... have proven themselves extremely fertile in producing so much musical material that many yet-to-be written pieces will undoubtedly explore further this particular labyrinth.

Footnotes

[1] Strictly speaking the sound is a *mutation* of the two spectra. The software used is **Soundhack**.

[2] The term 'pulse-rhythm' is used to refer to a rhythm derived from superimposing different pulse speeds. As an example, the 6:5 ratio produces a rhythm by superimposing the attacks from the values : (See also, music example below footnotes.)

mm=72	5/6	5/6	5/6	5/6...
mm=60	[1]	[1]	[1...	
mm=50	6/5	6/5	6/5..	

rhythm:	5/6	1/6	1/5	7/15	1/3	2/5	1/10	1/2	...etc.
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[3] GRM Tools.

[4] The string quartet chord is a version of the 6:5 pulse-rhythm's 'characteristic' harmony: the rhythmic values of the process yield 41 different values, but only 19 if repeats of the same value are omitted, and 9 if multiples of a value are omitted too (multiples of the same value would correspond to octave relationships in the spectrum derived from this process).

The 9 (or 19) values would correspond to partials **1**(2,4,8) **5**(10,20) **(3)6**(12,24) **7**(14) **9**(18) **13** **15** **19** and **25**. The partials in bold are played here - the fundamental is Bb.

[5] Stroppa, M., *The Analysis of Electronic Music*, Contemporary Music Review, Volume 1, Part 1 (1984): pages 175-180, G+B/Harwood

6:5